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Online Process Monitoring in Hybrid Injection Overmoulding

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Hybrid Injection Overmoulding

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- Combines properties of organosheets and injection moulding:
 - Excellent mechanical properties
 - High degrees of geometric freedom
 - Short cycle times
- Strength of hybrid structures determined by the interface between insert and injection moulding compound
- Incomplete understanding of process and lack of quality insurance

Online Process Monitoring

- Overmoulding tool for interface bonding specimen
- Sensor system for in-situ process monitoring inside the tool
 - Insert temperature
 - Melt temperature
 - Mould temperature
 - Melt front speed
- Definition of a process window for complete bond formation

Results

- Sensor system measures in-cavity temperatures online and throughout the injection process
- Study of the effects of various process parameters for PP-GF material system
- Interface bond strength most heavily influenced by:
 - Inset temperature
 - Melt temperature

ONLINE PROCESS MONITORING IN HYBRID INJECTION OVERMOULDING

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Motivation

- Hybrid injection overmoulding combines properties of organosheets and injection moulding:
 - Excellent mechanical properties
 - High degree of geometric freedom and short cycle times
 - Strength of hybrid structures is primarily determined by the interface between insert and injection moulding compound
 - Use for safety-critical parts (e.g. aerospace primary structures) is hindered by incomplete understanding of the process and lack of quality assurance

Operating principle of sensor-based process monitoring

Goals

- Tool development for fabrication of specimen and online process monitoring
- Measurement of electric process variables inside the mould cavity via integrated sensors
- Evaluation of tool and sensor system through a statistical test plan
- Study effects of various machine and process parameters on measured in-cavity process variables and bonding properties
- Definition of a process window for the complete bond formation between insert and injection moulding compound as a basis for quality assurance

Finished overmoulded PP-UF organosheet with overmoulded double lip structure

Overmoulding Tool & Test Specimen

- Test specimen for the determination of bonding properties at the interface
- Organosheet insert overmoulded with short-fibre reinforced thermoplastic ribs
- Double lip geometry to prevent bending of organosheet in tensile test
- Variable tool design allows variable insert thickness, injection sequence, distance from gate and creation of weld lines
- Wide range of processible materials up to high temperature thermoplastics such as PEEK

Sensor System

- Three different types and a total of eight sensors included in the tool
- Measurement of insert, mould and melt temperatures throughout the injection process
- Placement of sensors allows determination of melt flow rate in the cavity
- All sensors were provided to protect against FOD (Metallics) within the scope of the research project QuaSimOdo (Quality assurance in the overmoulding process-online)

Injection moulding tool
Tensile test specimen

Sensor positions inside the moulding cavity

Experimental Procedure

- Statistical test plan (DoE 2-plan with centre point, 170 parts, 500 tensile specimen) to determine effects of process and machine parameters
- Material system:
 - Insert: PP-UF organosheet; 2.6 mm; Bonding material: Torsar®-granulate
 - Injection moulding compound: PP-UF, short fibre reinforced; Borealis G825U
- Effects on in-cavity temperature, flow rate and bonding strength investigated
- Investigated process parameters:
 - Melt temperature
 - Tool temperature
 - Over temperature
 - Injection speed
 - Holding pressure

Process parameter	Lower level	Center level	Upper level
MeltTemp [°C]	230	240	250
ToolTemp [°C]	20	40	60
OverTemp [°C]	30	100	150
Injection speed [mm/s]	50%	100%	150%
Holding pressure [bar]	100	150	200

Statistical test plan (DoE 2-plan with centre point)

Results

- Statistically significant effects investigated:
 - for in-cavity temperature: Melt temperature
 - for flow rate: Injection speed, melt temperature
 - for interfacial bond strength: Over temperature, melt temperature, injection speed, tool temperature
- The bond strength as a main quality criteria is most heavily influenced by melt and over temperature, resulting in a higher interfacial temperature

Main effect plots for in-cavity temperature, flow rate and bond strength

Conclusion

- The developed test specimen is capable of indicating the effects of various process parameters on interfacial bond strength
- The integrated sensor system measures in-cavity temperatures of melt, insert and mould online and throughout the injection process
- Melt temperature and preheating of the insert have been identified as the most influential factors for high interface strength

- The developed process monitoring system will be transferred to high temperature thermoplastic materials within the scope of the HiQO (High Quality Overmoulding) research project
- For process validation a generic sensorised component will be manufactured
- Online measured process variables and quality assessment are stored in a electronic component file

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Thank you for your attention!

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